

A Study on the Socio-Economic Conditions of Khadi Artisans in Punjab

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Abstract:

Background

The heritage fabric Khadi is integral to the apparel sector in India. It holds a distinct identity due to its historical significance in bringing rural empowerment. However, this handspun fabric suffered a decline when the British promoted cotton farming, which was processed in mills and later flooded back into the Indian market, thus creating the downfall of Khadi. Mahatma Gandhi's Swadeshi Movement played a pivotal role in reviving Khadi, positioning it as a symbol of self-sufficiency, sustainability, and employment. The Indian government, particularly through the Khadi and Village Commission (KVIC), endeavors to promote Khadi. Punjab has contributed significantly to the Khadi movement and houses various Khadi manufacturing units. The present paper aims to study the Socio-Economic conditions of Khadi artisans in Punjab and evaluate the extent to which the KVIC has been able to accomplish its overall objectives in Punjab.

Methods

Various Khadi manufacturing units were visited, viz., Punjab Khadi Mandal at Hariana, a unit of Sutlej Khadi Mandal at Nakodar, and a unit of Kshetriya Punjab Khadi Mandal at Kharar. The spinners and weavers working in these units were interviewed using a purposive sampling technique. The study explored demographic and socio-economic profiles, including gender, age, qualification, annual income, work experience with KVIC, etc.

Results and Conclusion

The data gathered through analysis revealed that Khadi artisans are disappointed due to very low wages, irregularity in employment, drudgery involved, and little social security. Consequently, the younger generation in the artisan's families is hesitant to continue in their profession and has resorted to alternative sources of income.

Keywords: Employment, Heritage, Khadi, Khadi Artisans, Socio-Economic, Sustainable

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1. Introduction

The wearing of apparel is solely a human feature and is an essential element of society. People started wearing garments after the last Ice Age [1]. The Indian textile industry contributes around 2.3% to the GDP, 7% to manufacturing production, and 13% to the export earnings of the country. It is also the second-largest employer, employing around 45 million people as of 2019–20 [2]. A hand-spun Indian heritage fabric, Khadi, is also an integral part of the apparel segment [3, 4].

Originating from the word "khaddar," Khadi is a handcrafted textile created with the help of a charkha, a common instrument used in Indian villages for ages. This hand-spun Indian heritage fabric, Khadi, was stolen by the British. The East India Company promoted cotton farming, which was processed in mills as a textile and was later flooded back into the Indian market, thus creating the downfall of Khadi. Mahatma Gandhi initiated Khadi spinning for rural self-employment and self-sufficiency, thereby making Khadi an intrinsic part and emblem of the Swadeshi movement. He held out a fragile cotton thread as a sign of power and independence, as well as providing employment for millions. As a result, Khadi became India's national fabric and a symbol of India's freedom

struggle. The motive behind this movement lies in the fact that Gandhiji saw Khadi as a means to elevate the masses [5, 6].

The tradition of wearing cloth made by human hands has persisted to this day [7-9]. Khadi continues to be the main source of employment for the spinners and weavers throughout the country because they cannot find an alternate source of employment at their doorsteps. Khadi is helping to support destitute, helpless rural women so they can work independently and earn their living [10 -12].

1.1 Techniques of Khadi Making

Since its inception, Khadi production has gone through a lot of technological advancements. Improvements have been made at various stages, such as spinning, weaving, finishing, etc., to improve the quality, productivity, overall efficiency, and wages of all classes of Khadi workers [13, 14]. The performance and design of the spinning instrument have undergone extensive improvements. In the early days, the raw cotton was spun using a straightforward device called a "takli." The Takli was 10 to 14 inches long and thick, like a big needle made of iron with a brass circle at the bottom (Fig. 1) [15-20].

Figure 1: Takli used for spinning cotton Khadi

Image Source: <https://spinoffmagazine.com/troubleshoot-your-takli-spindle/>

Charkha was later introduced as a more efficient tool for spinning yarns and was mostly made from wood. Bardoli Charkha and Yerwada Charkha were the two major varieties of charkha used for spinning during the freedom struggle. Bardoli charkha is a regular form with a spinning wheel (Fig. 2). This is the oldest known type of spinning wheel that works by turning the drive wheel by hand while the yarn spins off the spindle tip. Artisans use a variety of Bardoli charkhas to spin the yarn [21, 22].

Figure 2: Bardoli Charkha

Image Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Spinning_wheel

Mahatma Gandhi had a need for a device that could be easily transported while he was in Yerwada jail, and so he created the Yerwada Charkha, or Peti Charkha (Fig. 3), which was a box-shaped device that was efficient, portable, and foldable. This was due to the fact that the traditional Charkha was cumbersome and difficult to transport. This portable spinning wheel was compact and could be folded into a small wooden box and carried with a handle. [15]

Figure 3: Yerwada Charkha or the Peti Charkha

Image Source: <https://charkhatales.com/blogs/chronicles-of-a-charkha/chronicles-of-a-charkha>

The introduction of KVIC's ring spinning technology, featuring multiple spindles ranging between two and twelve, has led to the development of new Charkhas. These modern Charkhas enable faster speeds and higher wages for spinners. While the majority of wheel spinning now occurs in the New Model Charkha (NMC) (Fig. 4), traditional hand-spinning wheels are still being used in rural villages. The spun yarns are wound into reels, each measuring 1000 meters [15].

Figure 4: New Model Charkhas

Image Source: <https://www.kvic.gov.in/kvicres/snt.php>

Currently, Khadi is viewed as a transformational fabric that is a fusion of traditional and modern heritage. It is worldwide preferred for its versatile features, resembling cotton in texture yet as supple as silk. Khadi is renowned for its eco-friendliness, adaptability to easy printing and embroidery, cooling properties in summer and warmth in winter, bucolic and unpretentious appearance, and skin-friendly characteristics owing to its breathable nature [16].

1.2 Khes and Phulkari: The Heritage of Punjab

Despite facing adversity, Indian artisans have withstood the test of time and have kept their great crafts alive. Over the centuries, handlooms have come to be associated with excellence in India's artistry in fabrics. The fabrics and designs of the region are influenced by its geographic, religious, and social customs. Different parts of India have produced distinct styles: the muslin of Chanderi, Varanasi brocades, Rajasthan, and Orissa have given tie and die products; Patola sarees from Patan; himroos of Hyderabad; phulkari and khes from Punjab; Daccai and Jamdani from Bengal; traditional designs from Assam and Manipur like the Phenek and Tongam. Indian handloom designs and weaves have been famous the world over, and it is important to ensure the sustenance of our cultural heritage [23].

The term "Phulkari" refers to Punjabi traditional needlework. Although it refers to flowers, the designs also feature geometrical patterns, which consist of flowers (phul) and shapes (akari). This style of clothing art is created on kurtis, dupattas, stoles, sarees, salwar suits, and juttis. The origin of the craft is debated. Some scholars suggest that it was introduced to India from Central Asia by the Jat community in the late medieval period, while others state that the craft was influenced by Persian gulkari embroidery designs. Phulkari embroidery and the traditions surrounding it have been mentioned in the Sikh holy book Guru Granth Sahib and the eighteenth-century Punjabi epic Heer Ranjha [23].

Phulkari embroidery is done using a running stitch with brightly colored untwisted silk thread, historically imported from Kashmir and Bengal. It uses a base of coarse hand-woven cloth called khaddar (or khadi), typically comprising strips about half a meter wide, or less, stitched together. In most cases, the khaddar is traditionally dyed red using

plant-based dyes obtained from palash (*Butea monosperma*) flowers, madder root (genus *Rubia*), or the bark of acacia (genus *Acacia*) trees. Embroidery threads are often yellow, orange, or pink; darker colors like black, brown, and green are less frequently used, and blue is rarely used [23–25].

Another important heritage of Punjabi textiles is khes, which has its roots in Khadi. Khes is a floor spread and bed covering that is traditionally made of cotton. The thinner ones are used as bed coverings in winter, and the thicker ones are used in place of shawls during winter. For generations, women residing in the villages of Punjab, have woven khes with bold, harmonic, and imaginative color patterns as a part of the trousseau they take to their future homes [22].

1.3 Emergence of KVIC

Khadi was brought to the people of undivided India in the year 1918 with the aim of achieving self-reliance and breaking away from British textiles. However, in May 1915, the Khadi movement, a socio-cultural story, was initiated by Mahatma Gandhi from the ashram of Satyagraha, Sabarmati, in the district of Ahmedabad, Gujarat [18]. Khadi became an important part of the national movement in 1921, and in 1923, the All-India Khadi Board, overseen by the Indian National Congress, was established to manage the growth of the Khadi program. Another organization, the All-India Spinners Association, also known as Akhil Bharat Chakra Sangh, was founded in 1925. Despite its close ties to the Indian National Congress, the All India Spinners Association (AISA) was an autonomous organization that focused on the manufacturing, marketing, and promotion of Khadi products until 1935 [25–28].

Later, with the efforts of Mahatma Gandhi, a system for providing a fair wage to Khadi spinners was devised in 1938. In addition to standardizing wages, Gandhi also emphasized the importance of Khadi, emphasizing its self-sufficiency and decentralization of supply and demand.

He personally got in touch with Khadi workers and contributed greatly to their economic development. After gaining independence in 1947, the AISA formulated a robust plan to generate employment in rural regions, simultaneously addressing the nation's demand for Khadi through hand spinning and hand weaving [29, 30]. The All India Khadi and Village Industry Board was established in January 1953. The All India Khadi and Village Industry Board replaced the Akhil Bhartiya Sarva Sangh, which had merged with the AISA [18]. Later in 1957, the Khadi and Village Industries Commission was created to address some procedural issues that were preventing the growth of the KVI program in India, as well as to publicize and uplift the growth and trade of Khadi products [12].

The Khadi and Village Industries Program played a significant role in providing rural artisans with more targeted service opportunities for the weaker strata of the culture [21]. KVIC is charged with organizing, developing, coordinating, and using projects for the improvement of Khadi and other town ventures in rural areas in collaboration with other offices involved in rural progress wherever necessary. Additionally, it develops a stockpile of raw materials and finished goods for distribution to manufacturers, establishes standard support offices for handling raw materials as semi-finished goods, and sets up offices for the marketing of KVI products apart from the preparation of craftsmen engaged in these enterprises and the facilitation of cooperative efforts among them.

1.4 Role and Functions of KVIC

The Khadi and Village Industries Commission (KVIC) falls under the Ministry of Small and Medium Enterprises, which oversees the sector's manufacturing, sales, distribution, and marketing processes [13]. The KVIC was established with the following fundamental goals in mind: (a) Social Goal: To develop non-farm job prospects in rural regions at wages that are, at the very least, equivalent to the current levels of salaries in the agricultural sector outside the peak season. (b) Economic Goal: to create salable items for the provision of services for which there is an actual demand. (c) Wider Objective: To encourage rural development in all of its forms and to raise living standards. Through its twin programs of Khadi and Village Industries Commission, KVIC has contributed to the creation of job possibilities in the unorganized rural non-farm sector.

Khadi refers to the production of handloom textiles, and Village industries include additional handicrafts and small, home-based businesses including lime production, beekeeping, oilseed processing, home-made soap, handmade paper, and fruit processing and canning. Planning, promoting, organizing, and assisting in the execution of plans

for the development of Khadi and Village Industries are typically the responsibilities of the KVIC. In order to do this, it undertakes the following activities: (a) funding of eligible agencies; (b) training of individuals working in or seeking employment in the Khadi and Village Industries, supervisors, and other officials; and (c) developing the material reserves. Among other things, this includes (d) research and development in the field of Khadi and Village Industries; (e) promoting the selling and marketing of Khadi and Village Industries products; and (f) promoting and encouraging cooperative efforts among the people involved in Khadi and Village Industries, among other activities [21, 22, 23].

Over the past couple of years, the primary objective of KVIC has been to generate sustainable employment for the artisans and young people who are out of work. In 2022–23, the KVIC achieved a milestone of creating 9.5 lakh jobs in rural areas. Over 80% of the Khadi units are established in rural areas. More than 50% of the units are led by SC, ST, and women entrepreneurs [16].

1.5 Khadi movement in Punjab

Punjab has contributed significantly to the Khadi movement. Following the Non-Cooperation Movement's suspension, Gandhiji carried out a number of initiatives to further the Swadeshi policy. Adampur, in Punjab, was famed for its weavers with a tradition of hand woven fabrics. There is a story that local craftsmen in Adampur welcomed Mahatma Gandhi with cotton garlands weaved by hand rather than flowers when he arrived in 1925. Gandhiji, a strong supporter of Khadi, considered it a vital instrument for the Swadeshi movement. Moved by the fervor of the Adampur artisans, he founded the All India Spinners Association and established its first office there. The weavers of Adampur helped the independence struggle by making Khadi more popular than English-imported textiles and opening up jobs for artisans in the villages. Hundreds of weavers and spinners were employed in making durris, khes, shirts, towels, and other items. Later, the center encompassed regions up to Jammu, Kashmir, and Delhi. During the Freedom Struggle, the Punjab Charkha Sangh was instrumental in popularizing and promoting Khadi [28].

However, in post-independence popular culture, the perception of Khadi altered, and its popularity dropped in Punjab as a result of a lack of diversity, design, innovation, and cheaper substitutes in the market. Due to changes in lifestyle and the rise of the latest technology, the demand for Khadi products decreased tremendously. The production of blankets and hosiery garments dented the Khadi market, and demand for Khadi products decreased. As demand continued to decline, weavers and spinners scattered across the country [15, 25, 28]. Most of the Khadi institutions are facing problems like a lack of working capital and financial assistance to improve retail outlets. Khadi stores in Punjab are flooded with unsold stocks of durris, khes, and towels [24]. The decline in demand for Khadi goods has hugely impacted the lives of Khadi artisans (spinners and weavers) in Punjab.

2. Objectives

This paper primarily aims at studying the socio-economic conditions of Khadi artisans in Punjab.

3. Material and Methods

The present paper aims to study the socio-economic conditions of Khadi artisans in Punjab and evaluate the extent to which the KVIC has been able to accomplish its overall objectives in Punjab. Following is the research methodology that opted to study the same.

3.1 Locale of the study

To carry out the survey, the researchers visited various Khadi manufacturing units, viz., Punjab Khadi Mandal at Haryana (a town in Hoshiarpur district), Sutlej Khadi Mandal at Nakodar, and Kshetriya Punjab Khadi Mandal at Kharar. Permission was sought from these Mandals to interview spinners and weavers working in these Mandals.

3.2 Population of the Study

All the respondents, both male and female artisans, were interviewed.

3.3 Sample Size

A total of 31 artisans (depending on availability), comprising 23 spinners and 8 weavers, were taken as a sample for the above study.

3.4 Data Collection

This study primarily used primary data, and to collect data, researchers used a semi-structured interview schedule containing open-ended and closed-ended questions. Secondary data was acquired from various government websites and publications related to KVIC.

3.5 Sampling Method

A purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the sample.

3.6 Time Span

This research was conducted from August 2022 to April 2023.

4. Results & Discussions

This part of the research paper presents the results regarding the socio-economic conditions of Khadi artisans in Punjab. Table 1–13 shows the demographic profile of the Khadi artisans in Punjab.

4.1 Gender

The respondents were asked a categorical question to determine their gender. For the response, they were asked to choose a male, female, or transgender option. The responses are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Gender of Khadi Artisans

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Male		Female		Others	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	8	100	0	-	0	-
Spinners	0	-	23	100	0	-

The data pertaining to gender revealed that in all the manufacturing units, all the spinners were female and all the weavers were male. However, female members of the weavers' family assist them in various tasks related to weaving.

4.2 Age

Age plays an important role. A higher number of years of age accounts for greater experience. Hence, age was also taken into consideration. Table 2 revealed that there were mostly experienced artisans who played a predominant role in Khadi.

Table 2: Age of Khadi Artisans

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Under 18 years		18-25 years		25-35 years		35-45 years		45-55 years		55-60 years		60 years and above	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	0	-	0	-	0	-	2	25	3	37.5	1	12.5	2	25
Spinners	0	-	0	-	3	13	4	17.4	6	26.1	4	17.4	6	26.1

It can be elucidated that all most of the weavers, and spinners are above the age of 45.

4.3 Qualification

It can be elucidated that most artisans have received little or no formal education (Table 3).

Table 3: Qualification of Khadi Artisans

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	No Schooling		Till Middle or Below		Matriculation		Senior Secondary		Bachelor's Degree		Master's Degree		Ph. D. or Higher	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	5	62.5	2	25	1	12.5	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Spinners	11	47.8	8	34.8	3	13	1	4.4	0	-	0	-	0	-

This implies that most of the artisans have only practical knowledge that they have learned from their elders.

4.4 Work Experience

Data on work experience shows that 50% of weavers have been with KVIC for 30 years or older, while the majority of spinners (56.7%) have been with KVIC for 20 years or more (Table 4).

Table 4: Khadi Artisans' Work Experience with KVIC

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	0-5 years		5-10 years		10-15 years		15-20 years		20-25 years		25-30 years		Above 30 years	
	N	%	N	%	No	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	0	-	0	-	0	-	1	12.5	2	25	1	12.5	4	50
Spinners	3	13	1	4.6	3	13	3	13	7	30.4	2	8.7	4	17.6

It can be elucidated that most of the older workers possessed significant work experience, while the younger generation lacked expertise in the art of weaving Khadi.

4.5 Annual Income from Khadi

The data pertaining to income revealed that the annual income of 50% of weavers is between Rs 60,000 - Rs 80,000 (Table 5). Furthermore, they live with their families in free quarters given by Khadi Mandals, where they have free access to water and electricity. However, the majority of spinners earn between Rs 10,000 and Rs 20,000 a year. The majority of the artisans stated that irregular employment was the primary cause of their poor annual income.

Table 5: Approx. annual income of Khadi Artisans

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Less than 10,000/-		Rs 10,000/- 20,000/-		Rs 20,000/- 40,000/-		Rs 40,000/- 60,000/-		Rs 60,000/- 80,000/-		Rs 80,000'/- 1,00,000/-		Rs 1,00,000/-- 2,00,000/-	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	0		0		0	-	0	-	4	50	1	12.5	2	37.5
Spinners	3	13	14	60.9	3	13	3	13	0	-	0	-	0	-

4.6 Level of Satisfaction

It was revealed that most of the artisans are dissatisfied with their income from KVIC (Table 6), as the cost of living has risen and it is difficult to feed or support the family with such low income wages.

Table 6: Level of Satisfaction with Income from KVIC

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Highly Satisfied		Satisfied		Fine		Dissatisfied		Highly Dissatisfied	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	0	-	0	-	3	25	3	37.5	3	37.5
Spinners	3	13	2	8.7	4	17.4	11	47.8	3	13

4.7 Income from other sources

Respondents were also asked about their secondary source of income, and data showed that 50% of weavers work outside of KVIC to supplement their income (Table 7). However, because women must additionally care for household responsibilities, only a minority (13%) of spinners have a supplementary secondary source of income.

Table 7: Secondary source of income

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Yes		No	
	N	%	N	%
Weavers	4	50	4	50
Spinners	3	13	20	87

4.8 Family Structure

According to family structure data, the majority of artisans (weavers and spinners) lived in joint families (Table 8).

Table 8: Family Structure of Khadi Artisans

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Individual and there is no Family		Nuclear Family		Joint Family	
	N	%	N	%	No	%
Weavers	0	-	1	12.5	7	87.5
Spinners	0	-	8	36.4	15	63.6

4.9 Reasons to Join KVIC

The majority of weavers (75%) joined KVIC since weaving is their family's profession. However, ease of work, utilization of free time, no investment, and financial support for the family were identified as important factors for spinners joining KVIC (Table 9).

Table 9: Reasons to Join KVIC

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Family Profession		No Investment		Ease of work		Utilization of free Time		Financial Support to the family		No other option		Others	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	6	75	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	2	25	0	-
Spinners	1	4.3	8	34.8	18	78.3	16	69.6	8	34.8	2	8.7	1	4.3

4.10 Technology prevailing in the Khadi Industry

During the survey, an investigation was also done on the type of technology used in the spinning and weaving of Khadi. Tables 10.1 and 10.2 represent the data pertaining to the types of charkha and loom used.

Table 10.1: Types of Charkhas Used by Spinners

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	N	%
Bardoli (Traditional) Charkha	10	43.48
Yerwada (Peti) Charkha	4	17.39
New Model Charkhas	6	26.09
Both Bardoli and New Model Charkhas	3	13.04

It was found that most of the spinners are still using old models of Charkhas, i.e., Bardoli (traditional) Charka (43.48%) and Yerwada (Peti) Charkha (17.39%). Only 26.09% of spinners are using New Model Charkhas (NMC). However, 13.04% of spinners are using both Bardoli and New Model Charkhas depending on the type of yarn required.

Table 10.2: Types of looms used by weavers

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	N	%
Simple Horizontal Loom (beaten in place by Panja, Metal Beater) for weaving of Panja Durris	4	50
Pit Loom	4	50

It was reported that nearly half of weavers were using simple horizontal looms for making Panja Durris, whereas the other half were using Pit looms.

4.11 Review of artisans on changes observed in the technology of Khadi Manufacturing

As far as new technology is concerned, weavers at Punjab Khadi Mandal and Sutlej Khadi Mandal unanimously stated that they had not seen any improvements in weaving technology over the years. They continue to weave the same Panja Durris on the same looms.

Weavers for the Kshetriya Punjab Khadi Mandal mentioned a shift from hand looms to pit looms. However, they expressed greater comfort with handlooms.

Spinners of Punjab Khadi Mandal stated that they had been using the same Peti Charkhas for years. The remaining spinners, on the other hand, were familiar with New Model Charkhas (higher spindles) and acknowledged their advantages. A significant number of them have adopted these New Model Charkhas.

4.12 Challenges at the Workplace

Data pertaining to workplace challenges (Table 11) revealed that artisans faced significant challenges such as lesser wages and income when compared to hard work, irregularities in employment, and job-related health issues. Artisans said that they are experiencing pain in their knees, arms, and back, as well as respiratory issues and irritation in the eyes and skin due to exposure to cotton fibers.

Table 11: Challenges being faced by the artisans at the workplace

(N=Total number of respondents; N=31)

	Less Wages		Improper Infrastructure		Income is less when compared to hard work		Irregularity in employment		Less Awareness about government schemes		Less awareness about Technology		Facing Health Issues	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Weavers	8	100	3	37.5	8	100	4	50	2	25	3	37.5	4	50
Spinners	20	86.9	0	-	16	69.5	16	69.5	0	-	0	-	7	30.4

Spinners mentioned that earlier Khadi Mandals used to provide them consistent work throughout the year, but after the COVID-19 pandemic, work is very irregular, and sometimes they don't get employment for 2-3 months.

The spinners working for Punjab Khadi Mandal, Adampur of Nazian village (at town Haryana), mentioned that they were facing a huge issue in cotton collection and transporting spun yarn. The absence of a collection center in their village forces them to struggle with the inconvenience of traveling with bulky bundles of cotton and spun yarn, which is particularly challenging when relying on public transportation.

4.13 Training Programs attended

A significant percentage of both spinners (91.3%) and weavers (87.5%) said that they have not attended any training programs organized by Khadi Mandals.

4.14 Suggestions for the Government and KVIC by Khadi Artisans

Increment in wages, regular employment, implementation of a pension plan for artisans, support with advanced Charkhas and looms, and the introduction of innovative designs and technologies in Khadi making were among the primary suggestions opined by Khadi artists. These suggestions reflect the artisans' aspirations for better working conditions and enhanced support from the government and KVIC.

5. Conclusion

The data obtained from the survey revealed that technology in Khadi making has not advanced much. Artisans face challenges due to the absence of advanced charkhas, looms, workplace amenities, and toolkits, resulting in low production and inconsistent product quality. Despite working diligently, Khadi artisans are susceptible to low wages and irregular employment, making it challenging to sustain a basic standard of living. Resultantly, the number of Khadi artisans in Punjab has drastically reduced, with artisans seeking opportunities in labor-intensive fields for better pay and improved social and economic security.

The study reveals that innovation, including the adoption of higher spindle Charkhas and more advanced looms, holds the key to overcoming these challenges. This shift would involve less drudgery and fetch more wages. Recognizing the significance of a diverse range of products, new designs, and quality offerings influencing

customer behavior, the study underscores the potential of innovation and improvement in Khadi fabric and garment design to boost sales, thereby creating more opportunities for Khadi artisans and fostering prosperity.

6. Suggestions for upgrading Khadi

Khadi, being a symbol of livelihood and self-sufficiency and an integral part of India's independence movement, serves as a crucial support for cottage industries. In Punjab, with its extensive history and significant potential, there is a unique opportunity to further promote and advance the cause of Khadi. Additionally, Khadi is intricately linked with the rich heritage of Punjab, including traditional textiles like Phulkari and Khes. To preserve these cultural treasures and bolster the promotion of Khadi and its products, it is imperative for the state government to implement measures that increase the demand for Khadi.

- The KVIC should organize training programs for artisans where the artisans should be made aware of the latest technologies and current trends.
- The government should facilitate the artisans with better work sheds, advanced toolkits and charkhas, and modern looms, which would involve less drudgery, better production, and fetching more wages.
- The government's national minimum wage system should be applicable in the Khadi sector, and artisans should benefit from it, as this is the only source of income for most of the artisans.
- The improvisation in the design of Khadi products needs to be undertaken to encourage the production of high-value-added products, which may lead to the increased sale of Khadi products.
- The marketing and branding of Khadi products should be stronger to compete with other global brands.
- There is a necessity to raise awareness about Khadi among buyers who seek high-quality and sustainable fabrics.
- The young buyer needs to be initiated into the sustainable properties of Khadi, as they are carbon-neutral and environment-friendly, plus they are handcrafted. Moreover, Khadi is a service to the nation as it provides employment to rural people.

References:

- [1] Fred David. 'Fashion, culture, and identity', University of Chicago Press: 1994
- [2] T. K. Shackelford & V. A. Weekes-Shackelford, Encyclopedia of evolutionary psychological science. Cham: Springer International Publishing: 2021
- [3] Jigna Chandrakant Trivedi, "A Study on Challenges Faced By the Khadi Marketers in Selling Khadi Apparels" Towards Excellence, 13/3 (1-16), (Sep' 2021)
- [4] Investindia.gov.in. [Updated 2020 Aug 07; 2023 Oct], <https://www.investindia.gov.in/sector/textilesapparel#:~:text=The%20domestic%20textiles%20and%20apparel,employment%20to%2045%20million%20people>
- [5] Upinder Kaur & Hitender Singh Rathore, "Globalization, Youth and Khadi", Journal of National Development, 30/2 (41-50), (2017)
- [6] Kvic.gov.in. Khadi Book, [updated 2018 ;cited Oct 5], https://www.kvic.gov.in/kvicres/update/e_Book/mobile/index.html
- [7] Fibre2fashion.com. Khadi: The Pride of India. [Updated 2011 Feb; cited 2023 Oct 5], <https://www.fibre2fashion.com/industry-article/5429/khadi-pride-of-india>
- [8] K. N. Chatterjee, D. Das, Kavita R. K. Nayak, "Study of Handle and Comfort Properties of Poly- Khadi, Handloom and Powerloom Fabrics", Man-made Textiles in India, 39/10 (351-359), (Oct'2011)
- [9] Economicstimes.indiatimes.com. Inefficiency spins Mahatma's Khadi dream into a nightmare, [updated 2017 Feb 18; cited 2024 Jan 11], <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/cons-products/garments/-/textiles/inefficiencyspins-mahatmas-khadi-dream-into-a-nightmare/articleshow/57213971.cms?from=mdr>
- [10] Economicstimes.indiatimes.com, Khadi: All set for a makeover [2019 Jul 08; cited 2023 Nov 17], <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/small-biz/sme-sector/khadi-all-set-for-a-makeover/making-khadi-popular-worldwide/slideshow/70126103.cms?from=mdr>
- [11] Shambu Chebrolu Prasad, "Exploring Gandhian Science: A Case study of the Khadi Movement", Doctoral dissertation, IIT Delhi, (Sep'2001)
- [12] Nitish Goel & Kshitij Jain, "REVIVAL OF KHADI – AN ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF KHADI IN INDIA WITH SUPPLY AND DEMAND SIDE PROBLEMS", Innovative Journal of Business and Management, 4/5,(100-103),(Sep-Oct'2015)
- [13] Khushboo Singh, Punita Raj Laxmi & Shakti Singh, "Reviving Khadi: From Freedom Fabric to Fashion Fabric", Man-Made Textiles in India, 42/11(409) (Nov'2014)

- [14] P. Gopinath, “WAGES, WORKING CONDITIONS AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC MOBILITY OF SPINNERS AND WEAVERS IN THE UNORGANISED KHADI INDUSTRY: FINDINGS FROM A SURVEY IN INDIA”, Indian Journal of Labour Economics, 53/2 (305-338), (Apr’ 2010)
- [15] kvic.gov.in . Science and Technology, [cited Oct ‘2023] <https://www.kvic.gov.in/kvicres/snt.php>
- [16] tribuneindia.com. A sad spin in Punjab khadi tale, [updated 2017 Jan; cited 2023 Nov 30], https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/archive/features/a-sad-spin-in-punjab-khadi-tale-344365#google_vignette
- [17] Simardeep Kaur & Radha Kashyap, “Market Scenario of Khadi with Special Reference to Punjab and Haryana”, Journal of Arts, 11/2 (223-236) (2022)
- [18] Anandi Sarkar Pyne, “An Exploratory Study on Khadi Industry of India”, Available at SSRN 2947509, (May’2017)
- [19] Pradnya P. Ambre and Sugandha Lad, “Khadi–Awareness and Promotion among Youth”, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology, 4/7 (2149-2153), (Jul’2017)
- [20] Lekshmi R Nair and D Dhanuraj, “Evaluation of Government Interventions in Khadi Sector”, Centre for Public Policy Research, (Jan’2016)
- [21] Shruti Gupta, Deepali Rastogi and Ritu Mathur, “Khadi: An Iconic Indian Cloth”, Journal of Applied Sciences, 5 /1 (267-278), Jan’ 2018)
- [22] Shruti Gupta, “THE CHANGING FACE OF KHADI: a heritage fabric”, Proceedings of the 24th IFFTI Conference 5 th -8 th April 2022 Nottingham Trent University, (147-162)
- [23] Ms. Priyanka Raghani and Dr. Jigna Trivedi, “A STUDY ON CHALLENGES FACED BY THE KHADI MARKETERS IN SELLING KHADI APPARELS”, Towards Excellence, 13/3 (782-795), (Sep’2021)
- [24] khinkhwab.com.Phulkari - The dyeing embroidery of Punjab [updated 2022 Sep11; cited Jan 2024],<https://khinkhwab.com/blogs/news/phulkari-the-dyeing-embroidery-of-punjab>
- [25] Anu H. Gupta and Shalina Mehta, “Patterns of Phulkari: Then and Now”, Bonfring International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Science,4/4 (179-185),(Nov’2014)
- [26] Hali.com. Phulkari exhibition, Turin. [Updated 2016 May 31; cited 2024 January 10], <https://hali.com/news/phulkari-exhibition-turin/>
- [27] hci.gov.in/kampala. Brief on Handloom Sector, <https://hci.gov.in/kampala/?pdf13218?000>
- [28] M. Alaguraja, Dr. G. Nedumaran & Manida M, “Performance of Khadi and Village Industries Commission Through Micro, Small, & Medium Enterprise”, Aegaeum Journal, 8/3, (April’ 2020)
- [29] Pib.gov.in. Strengthening Traditional Industry of Khadi in India, [updated 2023AUG 04; cited 2023 September],<https://pib.gov.in/FeaturesDeatils.aspx?NoteId=151549&ModuleId%20=%202>
- [30] Amritmahotsav.nic.in. Khadi - An Important National Icon of the Freedom Movement [updated 2023 November; cited 2024 January],<https://amritmahotsav.nic.in/district-repository-detail.htm?8941>

Websites Visited for Image Sourcing

- <https://spinoffmagazine.com/troubleshoot-your-takli-spindle/>
- <https://charkhatales.com/blogs/chronicles-of-a-charkha/chronicles-of-a-charkha>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Spinning_wheel
- <https://www.kvic.gov.in/kvicres/snt.php>